

RESPIRATORY TRACT MICROBIOCENOSIS DISORDERS IN CHILDREN WITH ACUTE STENOTIC LARYNGOTRACHEITIS

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Annotation. Acute respiratory diseases are the leading pathology of childhood. Their share together with influenza is not less than 70% in the structure of all morbidity in children. The increase in acute respiratory viral infections, accompanied by airway obstruction, among which stenotic laryngotracheitis has the great specific weight is noted during the last years.

Key words: Acute respiratory diseases, recurrent laryngotracheitis

The aim of the study was to investigate shifts in the microbiocenosis of the respiratory tract of children in both primary and recurrent laryngotracheitis.

Material and methods of investigation. The microbial landscape of mucous membranes of the upper respiratory tract (URI) was studied in 107 children at the age from 6 months to 5 years with acute stenotic laryngotracheitis by standard methods of bacteriological examination, including culture of nasopharyngeal and oropharyngeal secretions on nutrient media with subsequent identification. All examined children were divided into 2 groups according to the forms of acute stenotic laryngotracheitis according to the classification of Y. V. Mitin (1986): - Group I of 48 (44.4%) children with primary stenotic laryngotracheitis.(PSLT) - Group II of 59 (55.6%) with recurrent stenotic laryngotracheitis.(RSLT)

Results and discussion. According to our data, OSLT develops more frequently in young children (from 6 months to 3 years). In group I - patients with PSLT the majority of children (60,7%) fell ill between 1 and 3 years of age, 16,4% of children fell ill before the age of 1 year, and 23,0% - between 3 years and older. In group II - with PSLT the picture was somewhat different, the incidence at age 3 years and older was almost 3 times higher than in group 1. We compared the pattern of respiratory tract dysbiotic changes in the acute period of the disease depending on the age of our patients, and noted frequent mucosal lesions by *Staphylococcus aureus* in all age groups. Conclusions: Thus, in acute period of PSLC in children from 6 months to 3 years, the most severe violations of mucocoenosis of respiratory tract mucosa both in nasopharynx and oropharynx (normal composition of microflora in 9.5% and 9% of examined children respectively) were detected.

Literature:

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